
Application of Green Synthesis Ag-NPs from *Lawsonia inermis* (Henna) Plant as Antifungal & Non Toxic Nonmaterial in Drinking Water Purification

Samah Abdel Razik Mohamed

Housing & Building National Research Center, Sanitary & Environmental Engineering Institute
Manager of Microbiology lab for Water and wastewater Analyses, Egypt

Abstract The application of nanoparticles for drinking water purification can be summarized for three major types of contaminants: halogenated organics including pesticides, heavy metals and microorganisms. Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) can be prepared by various methods including chemical reduction, electrochemical techniques, and photochemical reduction. However, toxic compounds are usually involved. Our Study has focused on green synthesis of silver nanoparticles using leaf extract of *Lawsonia inermis* (Henna) plant to avoid using hazardous materials. Green synthesis Henna-AgNPs were characterized by UV-Visible Spectroscopy, SEM, EDXS. The antifungal activity were assessed for: (a) AgNO₃ solution, (b) Henna-AgNPs, (c) Lawsonia alba lam leaves extract (control) on tested fungal isolates using disc diffusion method. The results indicate different growth rating for the three testes solutions which proved that Green synthesis Henna-AgNPs has different antifungal activity against tested fungal strains as *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Penicillium notatum*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. The toxicity of the three testes solutions were carried out using MICROTOX ANALAYZIER and *Vibrio fischeri* showed that their toxicity degree occur in ranges (80-100) which indicate nontoxic. The goal of our study to assessment the use of *Lawsonia inermis* (henna plant) extract-AgNPs to apply in many applications the most important one water purification due to their antimicrobial activity against wide ranges of microbes that causes infectious diseases which have proven their antifungal efficacy which can offer viable alternative in terms of cost, efficient in action and less toxic without any side-effects.

Keywords Silver Nanoparticles, Antifungal Activity, Green synthesis of AgNPs, Henna leaves, Lawsonia Alba Lam, AgNO₃, Nano-Engineering, Characterization, water purification, toxicity, luminometer, bioluminescence, antibiotic resistance microbes

Introduction

Currently, WHO/UNICEF estimated that 783 million people in the world do not have access to safe drinking water and 1.87 million childhood deaths are due to water-borne diseases. Conventional water treatment and delivery approaches are considered unfeasible in these under-developed areas because they need high capital investments, a high cost of maintenance, a high quantity water source, and these require users to pay for the treated water. People have to collect their own water outside their homes and then store the water in the household due to the lack of water supply, and contaminations could occur during the water collection, transport, and storage, which cause a high chance of water-borne disease infection [1].

Nanotechnology is a growing field in which the understanding and control of matter in the scale is used to develop new solutions. It involves the manipulation of matter on a near atomic scale to produce new structure, devices, and materials. Nanotechnology has been explored for creating lighter and stronger materials, for remediating contaminated groundwater, for replacing toxic chemicals in various applications, for enhancing solar cell efficiency, and for targeted cancer treatment. The science is present in environmental remediation, pollution detecting sensors, photovoltaics, medical imaging, and drug delivery [2].

Silver nanoparticles can be synthesized using physical, chemical and biological reduction methods. Biological method for synthesis of nanoparticles uses plant based extracts, products, enzymes, reducing factors, proteins, peptides, antioxidants, triglycerides, saponins, glycoproteins, antioxidants, pigments, latex, gums, polysaccharides, phytochemical constituents like terpenoids, flavonoids, tannins and vitamins and cofactors for reduction and/or stabilization of nanoparticles. The synthesis of nanoparticles using plant extracts is often termed as green synthesis method that reduces or eliminates generation of hazardous substances [3].

Nanomaterials and their increasing use in manufactured products are of great concern to treatment systems and the environment. Nano silver has become one of the most popular nanoparticles due to its many applications and relatively low manufacturing costs. It is being used for a wide variety of commercial products including medical applications, water purification, antimicrobial uses, paints, coatings, food packaging. Impregnating other materials with silver nanoparticles is a practical way to exploit the germ fighting properties of silver [4].

The advantage of using green synthesis method for synthesis of silver nanoparticles over chemical and physical method is that it is stable due to plant peptides and proteins, economic, the by-products are non-toxic, the need of controlled physical parameters is reduced and have greater antibacterial and antifungal property. These nanoparticles are known to lyse the bacterial and fungal cell and thus have antagonistic effects, they find wide applications in the development of new pharmaceutical drugs, in reduction of burn infection and disinfection [5].

Realizing the nature of contaminants in drinking water and the need to remove them at ultra-trace levels, significant progress has been made in the recent past to utilize biogenic nanomaterials for water purification. This study is to measure the antifungal activity of henna -AgNPs and its toxicity for application in water purification.

Materials and Methods

All the reagents were of analytical grade and used without further purification. Silver nitrate was purchased from Fisher Scientific, USA. Sabroud dextrose agar is purchased from Lab M USA.

Plant Sample Collection, Extract preparation and Biological synthesis of Henna -AgNPs

The leaves of *L. Alba lam* (Henna) plant was collected freshly from local garden in Cairo, and was identified at the Department of Botany, Cairo University, Science College, Egypt. *Leaves of L. alba lam (Henna)* was collected and rinsed with tap water then by de-ionized water and allowed to dry in air. Then they were cut into small pieces. 20 grams was taken in conical flask containing 200 ml distilled water and boiled them for 10 minutes. After cooling, they are filtered using whatmann No.1 filter paper and kept at 4 °C for further work. Aqueous extract of plant (20 ml) was prepared is taken in conical flask and 180 mL of 1 M of AgNO_3 was added and kept at room temperature for reduction and change of color was observed. Entire process was carried out in darkness to avoid photo activation of AgNO_3 at room temperature [6].

Figure 1: (a) AgNO_3 solution, (b) Henna-AgNPs, (c) Alba lam henna leaves extract (control)

Microbiological Examination

The antifungal activity of green synthesis suspension Henna-AgNPs, AgNO₃ and Henna extract was carried against tested fungal strains as *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Penicillium notatum*, *fusarium oxysporum*, *saccharomyces cerevicae*.

Fungal Cultures

The tested fungal strains were isolated from drinking water and identified according to [7] at the Department of Botany, Cairo university, Science College, Egypt.

Preparation of Media

Sabroud dextrose agar medium was prepared and adjust pH to 7 & sterilized by autoclaving at 15 lbs pressure 121 °C for 15 min [8].

Antifungal Assay

Petri plates containing 20 ml of autoclaved and solidified Sabroud dextrose agar medium were inoculated by 100 µl of prepared spores suspension were then plated onto agar surface followed by impregnated disc after dried with the three examined solutions as follow(a: AgNO₃ b:Henna Ag-NPs of Henna extract c: Henna extract), gently pressed down to ensure contact and incubation at 28 °C for 28 days then Check each plate after incubation time and report results as the rating was recommended by [9-12] for each fungal isolates.

Table 1: Rating of fungal growth according to ASTM Test Method for Ability of adhesive films to support or resist the growth of fungi

Observed growth on specimens	Rating
None	0
Traces of growth (less than 10 %)	1
Light growth (10 – 30 %)	2
Medium growth (30 – 60 %)	3
Heavy growth (60 – 100 %)	4

Toxicity Test

1ml of each examined solutions a,b&c were added to 1l of autoclaved distilled water and the test carried and results recorded according to [13] by using Microtox and *Vibrio fischeri* bacteria as tested organism. The bacteria are exposed to three solutions in being tested. The reduction in intensity of light emitted from the bacteria is measured along with standard solutions and control samples. The results are normalized and the EC₅₀ (concentration producing a 50% reduction in light) is calculated using the software for Microtox Omni Azur.

Table 2: Toxicity degrees and EC₅ for three examined solutions (AgNO₃, Henna Ag- NPs and Henna extract)

Degree of toxicity	Extremely Toxic	Very Toxic	Toxic	Moderate Toxic	Non-Toxic
EC ₅₀ Value	0-19	20-39	40-59	60-79	80≥100

EC₂₀: The effective concentration causing 20% luminescence inhibition EC₅₀: The effective concentration causing 50% luminescence inhibition

Bacteria Storage temperature: -25 C °Reference substances used: 3,5-Dichlorophenol, Zinc sulfate hyptahydrate, Potassium dichromate

Characterization Techniques of Silver Nanoparticles

Characterization of synthesized henna-AgNPs by using UV-Vis Spectroscopy, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), X-Ray Diffractometer (XRD) is performed to understand their Physical & Chemical properties [14].

UV-vis Spectroscopy

The bio-reduction of Ag⁺ in aqueous solution was detected using UV-vis Spectrophotometer (Shimadzu 3600 NIR, Kyoto, Japan) at room temperature with wave lengths of 200-800 at a resolution of 1 nm.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Scanning electron microscope was used to characterize the surface of synthesized nanoparticles. The solution containing silver nanoparticles synthesized from *L. alba lam* leaf extract was inverted into powder using Lyophilizer

equipment. Thin films were prepared on carbon coated grids. These images of bio synthesized silver nanoparticles were obtained in SEM (Inspect FEI Ltd, Holland) operated at 30 KV at different magnification level.

Energy-Dispersive X-Ray (EDX) Analysis

The synthesized silver nanoparticles using *L. alba lam* (Henna) aqueous extract subject to the energy dispersive spectrum to confirm the presence of silver and to detect other elementary compositions of the particle.

XRD Analysis

The bio-reduced silver nanoparticles was made into powder using Lyophilizer equipment and they are coated on XRD grid and analyzed for the formation of nanoparticles using X-Ray diffractometer (X-Pert Pro, Panalytical, Holland), X-Ray generator operated at a voltage of 5 KV and tube current of 50 mA with Cu α_1 radiation with λ of 1.5406.

Results and Discussion

Visual observation

The synthesis of silver nanoparticles in the solution of 1 mM AgNO_3 and aqueous extract of *L. alba lam* (Henna) plant sample was confirmed by change in color of the mixture from dark brown to colloidal grey which indicates the formation of AgNPs compared to the control (without treatment with 1mM AgNO_3) that remained dark brown Fig. (1). It is well known that silver nanoparticles exhibit dark grey colour in water due to extinction of surface Plasmon vibration in metal nanoparticles [15]. Control (without silver nitrate) shows no color change, the colour change in the aqueous extract with silver nitrate solution may be due to the presence of bioactive compounds in aqueous extract like Gallic and Lawsone acid responsible for the reduction of silver nitrate to silver nanoparticles. The different type of various phytochemicals and antioxidants are responsible for the reduction of silver ions, similar type observations were reported by another authors [16-17].

UV-vis Spectral Analysis

The silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) formed by reduction of silver nitrate using aqueous extract of *L. alba lam* leaf after 24 hours incubation samples were characterized by UV-visible spectroscopy, and the results confirmed by the biological AgNPs formation in reaction mixture. In UV-visible spectrum, a broad peak located between (420 nm – 500 nm) was observed relatively uniform as shown in Fig. (2a), Fig. (2b). this reveals that the formation of AgNPs occurs rapidly within 2 hours for completion of the reaction. Similar observations were reported in Geranium, leaf extract [15]. In this study, the synthesized AgNPs were shown characteristic peak at 470 nm in visible light regions.

Figure 2: (a) Henna-AgNPs, (b) Henna Alba lam leaves extract (control)

SEM Analysis

SEM analysis shows AgNPs synthesized by *L. alba lam* (Henna) leaf extract. It was shown that relatively uniform and spherical AgNPs were formed with diameter of 14 to 65 nm, as shown in Fig. (3). The SEM image of silver nanoparticles was due to interaction of hydrogen bond and electrostatic interactions between the bioorganic capping molecules bound to the AgNPs. The larger silver nanoparticles may be due to the aggregation of the smaller ones, due to the SEM measurements.

Figure 3: (a,b) SEM Results of *Alba lam* (henna) extract, (c,d) SEM Results of *Alba lam henna* - AgNPs

EDX Analysis

EDX spectra recorded from the silver nanoparticles were shown in Fig. 4. From EDX spectra, it is observed that silver nanoparticles reduced by *L. alba lam* extract have the weight percentage of silver as 68 % and 28.2 %. The EDX spectrum spherical in shape with high aggregation of silver nanoparticles on the surface of the cell prepared with this bio reduction method using *L. alba lam* (Henna) shown maximum peaks around 3.4 KeV correspond to binding energies of silver ions. Some additional peaks belonging to bioorganic compounds present in the reaction mixture. The EDX analysis reveals strong signals in the silver region that confirms the formation of silver nanoparticles using biological source. There were other spectrum peaks for Cl, Si, O and Ca suggesting that they are mixed precipitates in the plant extracts [18].

Figure 4: EDX Results of Synthesized AgNPs of *L.alba Lam Henna*

XRD Analysis

The XRD patterns obtained for the AgNPs synthesized using Henna extract is shown in Fig.5. The Bragg reflections were observed in the XRD pattern at $2\theta = 32.1, 26.92, 45.41$ and 37.92 . These reflections clearly indicated the presence of (100), (52), (43) and (42) sets of lattice planes and further on the basis that they can be indexed as Face-centered-cubic (FCC) structure of silver [16] reported that the XRD pattern green synthesized silver nanoparticles showed number of Bragg's reflections that may be indexed on the basis of the face centered cubic structure of silver. Since, they present study clearly indicated the X-Ray diffraction pattern of biological synthesized silver nanoparticles formed crystalline.

Figure 5: XRD Results of Henna- AgNPs of *L. alba Lam (Henna)*

The antifungal activity

Water is absolutely necessary for life on earth. All living organisms require water for their creation, survival and evolution. Increased disposal of industrial, domestic and agricultural waste into water bodies and consequent pollution of water has become a major issue in the 21st century. Nanomaterials due to large surface area, easy surface modification and selective catalytic activity turned out to be an effective adsorbent for water purification [19].

Microbial colonization in water causes problems with dangerous effects caused by the influence of fungi on human health. Spores and mycelial fragments may contain toxic compounds called mycotoxins, which cause allergies. *Penicillium spp.* and *Aspergillus spp.* are to a significant degree responsible for the occurrence of many allergic symptoms and respiratory diseases diagnosed in people exposed to high levels of fungal spores and allergens. Using Henna Ag-NPs to determine their activity against tested fungal isolates.

(1:a) $AgNO_3$ solution with *fusarium oxysporum*

(1:b) Henna-AgNPs solution with *fusarium oxysporum*

(1:c) HennaAlba lam leaves extract (control) with *fusarium oxysporum*

(2:a) $AgNO_3$ solution with *penicillium notatum*

(2:b) Henna-AgNPs solution with *penicillium notatum*

(2:c) HennaAlba lam leaves extract (control) with *penicillium notatum*

(3:a) $AgNO_3$ solution with *saccharomyces cereviaece*

(3:b) Henna-AgNPs solution with *saccharomyces cereviaece*

(3:c) HennaAlba lam leaves extract (control) with *saccharomyces cereviaece*

(4:a) $AgNO_3$ solution with *Asperagillus flavus*

(4:b) Henna-AgNPs solution with *Asperagillus flavus*

(4:c) HennaAlba lam leaves extract (control) with *Asperagillus flavus*

Figure (6) the results of microbiological test on examined matters against different fungal isolates.

From figure (6:1:a, 6:2:a, 6:3:a, 6:4:a & 6:5:a) the most sensitive fungal isolates to $AgNO_3$ was *fusarium oxysporum*, and *saccharomyces cereiviaece* with rating growth 0 (non growth), rating 1 (2% trace growth) and 1 (9% trace growth) respectively, whereas the more resistant isolates were *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus* with rating 2 (30 % light growth) and rating 3 (30 % medium growth).

From figure (6:1:b, 6:2:b, 6:3:b, 6:4:b & 6:5:b) the most sensitive fungal isolates to Henna AgNPs was *fusarium oxysporum*, *penicilium notatum* and *saccharomyces cereiviaece* with rating growth 1 (1% trace growth), rating 1 (3% trace growth) and 2 (10% light growth) respectively, whereas the more resistant isolates were *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus* with rating 3 (40 % medium growth) and rating 3 (60 % medium growth).

From figure (6:1:c, 6:2:c, 6:3:c, 6:4:c & 6:5:c) the most sensitive fungal isolates to Henna extract was *fusarium oxysporum* and *saccharomyces cereiviaece* with rating growth 1 (9% trace growth), rating 2 (40% light growth) and 3 (50% medium growth) respectively, whereas the more resistant isolates were *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus* with rating 4 (70 % heavy growth) and rating 4 (80 % heavy growth).

As demonstrated by the above data and according to [20] *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus* is a more resistant pathogen of the two examined strains they known to be the most resistant pathogens among fungi. It may result from the activity of chemical components (such as ascorbic acid) which are produced by them. Nevertheless, the specific resistance mechanism needs to be further investigated in greater detail.

Henna -AgNPs makes it possible to achieve a high percentage of growth inhibition which inhibit the growth of *fusarium oxysporum*, *saccharomyces cereiviaece* and *penicilium notatum*, by 99% and 97% respectively. whereas inhibit the growth of *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus* by 60 % and 40 %. The obtained results confirm the efficiency of using Henna -AgNPs as a good green nanomaterial in water purification with antifungal properties.

Its antimicrobial activity is associated with the characteristic structure of nanoparticles. They are characterized by a high fraction of surface atoms so that nanoparticles have a greater affinity for interactions with thiol groups, which activity entails the destruction of bacteria. It exhibits a high antifungal activity against some pathogenic strains. This applies mostly to biomedical engineering, water purification cosmetology, food packaging industry, textile industry, crops, animal husbandry [21].

AgNP can inactivate abroad spectrum of microorganisms. Previous studies have proposed three mechanisms of the antimicrobial activities of AgNP: (i) Could attach to cell membrane and disrupt the permeability and respiration functions of the cell and thus kill the cells [22] (ii) Reactive oxygen species (ROS) can be generated on the surface of nanoparticles and cause damage of DNA by exerting oxidative stress; (iii) Silver ions released from AgNPs can also cause disruption of ATP production and DNA replication [23].

The Toxicity

Effective concentration (EC) for three solutions that result in 20% & 50% inhibition in Bioluminescence of *Vibro Fischeri* (EC_{50} & EC_{20}) values were calculated after 30 min exposure time at 25 °C.

Table 4: Effective concentrations and toxicity degrees for the three test solutions

Sample	EC ₅₀ (%)	EC ₂₀ (%)	Toxicity degree	pH before adjustment	pH after adjustment
Henna extract	91	36.4	non toxic	7.2	7.2
Henna-AgNPs	97	38.8	non toxic	6.5	7
AgNO ₃	89	32	non toxic	6	7.2

The susceptibilities of *V. fischeri* to silver ions were higher than of silver nanoparticles, indicating that it was more sensitive to the silver ions, then silver ions were more toxic than synthesized silver nanoparticles. Diffusivity of silver ions to the bacterial cells is more than that of the Ag-NPs. According to the EC, the toxicity decreased in the following order: Silver ions > silver nanoparticles from chemical reduction method > silver nanoparticles from biological method. It can be concluded that the bacteria *V. fischeri* is so sensitive to toxicity effects of chemicals and can be used as a biosensor for rapid and low-cost detection of acute toxicity of nanomaterials [24-25].

Conclusion

Silver is known for its potent antimicrobial properties. The production of the silver nanoparticles using chemical synthesis method became less applied due to use of toxic chemicals and precipitating agents to the environment. We have synthesized sustainable nanoparticles that prevent pollution by using reducing properties and enzymes of plant extracts. *Lawsonia inermis* (Henna) leaf extract was used effectively for nanoparticles synthesis, which was stable due to plant peptides, proteins and phytochemicals. They are known to lyse the bacterial and fungal cell and thus have potent antagonistic effects. They inhibited the fungal growth and thus they may find wide applications in the development of new drugs, in reduction of burn infection and in control of diseases and water purification, which is an economical, efficient and eco-friendly process and the characterization techniques viz., UV-Visible spectrophotometer, SEM, EDX, XRD have confirmed that the reduction of silver nitrate to silver nanoparticles is nontoxic to aquatic micro-organisms.

References

1. WHO/UNICEF, (2012). Progress on Drinking Water and Sanitation.
2. Morose, G., (2010). "The 5 principles of "Design for Safer Nanotechnology"." Journal of Cleaner Production: 285-289.
3. Rebecca, T.; Fenali, P.; Parvathi, L., (2012): Studies on antibacterial and antifungal activity of silver nanoparticles synthesized using *Artocarpus heterophyllus* leaf extract, Society for Applied Biotechnology; pISSN 2249-9075, eISSN 2249-9938, 2(1):632-637.
4. Nanotechnology, (2010). A to Z of Silver Nanoparticles-How They Are Providing Environmentally Friendly Antibacterial Properties In Consumer Goods.
5. Thombre, R.S.; Mehta, S.; Mohite, J.; Jaisinghani, (2013). Studies on antibacterial and antifungal activity of silver nanoparticles synthesized using *Artocarpus heterophyllus* leaf extract, Bio. Sci. 4:P184-192.
6. Satheesh, K.K. and Kathireswari, P., (2016). Biological synthesis of Silver nanoparticles (Ag-NPS) by *Lawsonia inermis* (Henna) plant aqueous extract and its antimicrobial activity against human pathogens, Int. J. Microbiol. App. Sci., 5(3):926-937.
7. Bennett, J.W. and Klich, M., (2003). Mycotoxins, Clinical Microbiology Reviews, 16(3), 497-516.
8. Standard Methods for the Examination Of Water and Wastewater, (2005). Water Works Assoc. (AWWA), Washington, D.C.
9. ASTM D4300-1 Standard Test Method for Ability of adhesive films to support or resist the growth of fungi
10. ISO 22196:2007 Standard Method for measurements of antimicrobial activity on plastic surface and non-porous surface.

11. Langfield, R. D.; Scarano, F. J.; Heitzman, M. E.; Kondo, M.; Hammond, G. B.; Neto, C. C. ,(2004). Use of a modified microplate bioassay method to investigate antibacterial activity in the Peruvian medicinal plant *Peperomiagaliodes*. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 94(2–3), 279–281.
12. Debabrat, B.; Nakul, S. and Rituparna, B., (2014). Green synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles using *Bryophyllum pinnatum* (Lam) and monitoring their antimicrobial activities; *Arch. Appl. Sci. Res.*, 4(5): 2098.
13. Water quality- Determination of the inhibitory effect of water samples on the light emission of *Vibrio fischeri* (luminescent bacteria test), part 3: using freeze- dried bacteria (ISO 11348-3:2007).
14. Choi, O.; Deng, K.K.; Kim, N.J.; Ross, L.; Surampalli, R.Y. and Hu, Z., (2008). The inhibitory effects of silver nanoparticles, silver ions and silver chloride colloids on microbial growth, *Water Research*, 42: 3066 – 3074.
15. Abhishek, M.; Akhilesh, K.; Vandana, D.;Garima, D. and Deep, S., (2014). Green Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles using medicinal plant and its characterization. *Der. Pharmacia. Sinica.*, (5):118 – 122.
16. Debabrat, B.; Nakul, S. and Rituparna, B., (2012). Green synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles using *Bryophyllum pinnatum* (Lam) and monitoring their antimicrobial activities, *Arch. Appl. Sci. Res.*, 4(5):2098.
17. Jayakumar, D.; Jhancy, M. and Jayasanthi, R., (2010). Evaluation of anti- Oxidant potential and Anti-Bacterial activity of *Calotropis gigantea* and *Vincarosea* using in-vitro model, *Ind. J. Sci. Technol.*, 3(7):720 – 723.
18. Usha, C; Gladys, A. and Rachel, D., (2014). Biogenic Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles by *Acacia nilotica* and their Anti-Bacterial Activity, *Int. Jour. Scientific*
19. Soujit, S. and Pradeep, T., (2016). Affordable and Clean Drinking Water Using Nanomaterials DST Unit on Nanoscience and Thematic Unit of Excellence, Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology Madras, Chennai-600 036, India.
20. Jolanta, P.; Marcin, B.; Renata, S. and Mirosław, B., (2013).Vol. 60, No 4/2013 795–798 on-line at: www.actabp.pl.
21. Kim, K.J.; Sung, W.S.; Moon, S.K.; Choi, J.S.; Kim, J.G. and Lee, D.G., (2012) Antifungal Effect of silver nanoparticles on dermatophytes. *J Microbiol Biotechnol* 18: 1482–1484.
22. Park, M.V., et al., (2011). The effect of particle size on the cytotoxicity, inflammation, Developmental toxicity and genotoxicity of silver nanoparticles. *Biomaterials*, 32(36): p. 9810-9817.
23. Kittler, S., et al., (2010), Toxicity of Silver Nanoparticles Increases during Storage Because of Slow Dissolution under Release of Silver Ions. *Chemistry of Materials*, 22(16): p. 4548-4554.
24. Ehsan, B.; Ali, A.; Safekordi, H.; Reza, S.; Mohammad, J. and Abasalt, H., (2012). Comparative toxicity study of two different synthesized silver nanoparticles on the bacteria *Vibrio fischeri*, *African Journal of Biotechnology* Vol. 11(29), pp. 7554-7564, DOI: 10.5897/AJB11.4050 ISSN 1684–5315 Academic Journals
25. Binaeian, E.; Rashidi, A. and Attar, H., (2012). Toxicity Study of Two Different Synthesized Silver Nanoparticles on Bacteria *Vibrio fischeri*, *World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology*, 67: 1219-1225.

